

MICROCREDIT FINANCE AFFECTING LOW-INCOME EARNERS IN DAVAO CITY

ABSTRACT

This study reviews the achievements of the microcredit finance revolution, through reference to the now extensive literature. It finds that there are many opportunities to improve and innovate. This paper concentrated on examining if Microcredit Finance is indeed helpful to the low-income earners in Davao City. The study aims to assess the significant difference in Microcredit Finance Affecting low-income Earners in Davao City. The researchers used a non-experimental quantitative research design using a correlational method to discern the difference and significance of the variables. The study was participated by the members of Microcredit Finance in Davao City, with 100 respondents. The method used for the selection of participating respondents was Purposive sampling. The data were analyzed and interpreted using the mean, standard deviation, and ANOVA: two-factor without replication as statistical tools. The results concluded that there is a significant difference between microcredit finance and low-income earners in Davao City.

Keywords: Microcredit finance, low-income earners, non-experimental quantitative-correlational, Davao City

INTRODUCTION

Microcredit is used to fight poverty and promote economic growth by providing small loans to the poor. This thesis examines microfinance's influence on poverty in Davao City, addressing the challenges of sustainable development through poverty reduction and economic viability. By combining these efforts, a balanced approach can be achieved for societal progress and a sustainable future (Ballester & Pilar, 2021). Microfinance overcomes barriers in rural areas, offering innovative lending techniques like group lending and uncollateralized loans. This drives socioeconomic growth, financial inclusion, and empowers underserved regions Maeenuddin, (S. Hamid, A. M. Nassir, et al., 2021); (Sangwan & Nayak, 2020). Financially unsustainable MFIs restrict their capacity to assist underprivileged individuals. When they struggle to cover expenses solely from loan interest income, achieving financial sustainability becomes imperative to avoid discontinuation and effectively support those in poverty (Maeenuddin, S. Hamid, A. M. Nassir, et al., 2021).

According to Wysktra, (2019), Microcredit has effectively provided financial services to the underprivileged, expanding their options for coping with irregular incomes. It plays a crucial role in improving lives, fostering self-employment, and promoting microbusiness development. By empowering individuals with specialized

financial services, microfinance institutions contribute to job creation, economic resilience, and overall development (Nogueira et al. 2020). Microfinance enables households to enhance income potential, break the poverty cycle, and support families. It assists underserved groups, including women, the elderly, and individuals with disabilities, in meeting basic needs and accessing entrepreneurial opportunities (Hansen et al. 2020). Microfinance enables lasting impacts as families save and invest in housing, healthcare, and education. It empowers entrepreneurs, creating job opportunities and fostering economic growth. Participating in microfinance initiatives improves consumption, nutrition, living standards, and economies (Nogueira et al. 2020).

The study “Micro Credit Financing Affecting the Low-income Earners in Davao City” examines small loans' effectiveness for low-income individuals in Davao City, focusing on their utilization and repayment strategies. Effective management of micro-credit services requires borrowers' commitment to repayment and prudent investment. Prompt and effective measures are needed to address poverty and elevate living standards. (Bent 2019). Research suggests that societies can only effectively combat poverty if they possess the necessary resources to swiftly revive income-generating economic endeavors, including small-scale farming, small businesses, and sole proprietorships. (Khan et al. 2020). Microfinance organizations reduce poverty by offering small loans, savings accounts, and insurance services to underserved individuals, empowering them to start businesses, increase income, save money, and manage financial risks. They promote inclusive economic growth and alleviate poverty by addressing specific needs (Tafamel 2019).

Married women have a higher probability of achieving personal and economic empowerment compared to single women due to their increased responsibilities. Their marital status also increases their chances of accessing microcredit (Ali, 2020). In a study conducted by Bwambale et al. (2021) in the Luwero District of Uganda, it was found that microfinance enables low-income earners to meet their families' needs. The study revealed that microfinance clients reported an overall mean score of 3.81, indicating that microfinance services helped them fulfill their basic needs and improve their financial capability. The study by "The editorial board" (2022) in rural areas and low-wage urban jobs, the poorest individuals are commonly found. Cooperatives play a crucial role in such circumstances, filling the gaps left by limited private businesses and inadequate government services. They provide members with benefits like agricultural resources, vocational training, sanitation initiatives, and community banking, contributing to community well-being and addressing member needs.

The level of monthly income exceeding 15,000 Philippine pesos and marital status are both important factors that can influence financial stability and well-being. Several studies and research have explored these aspects. A study by Ali (2020) explores the link between marital status and women's empowerment, finding that married women have a higher probability of personal empowerment and greater access to microcredit, leading to economic empowerment. In a study by Cabigon and Manalo (2020) on focuses on a jobs strategy for the Davao Region in the Philippines, exploring the impact of factors like income and marital status on economic development. It provides valuable insights into shaping employment opportunities and livelihoods. Another study by Ballester and Pilar (2021) explores

the connection between income level and sustainable development, emphasizing the role of income availability in achieving sustainable development goals and reducing poverty. It highlights the significance of considering income levels beyond 15,000 Philippine pesos and marital status in understanding financial empowerment, economic development, and poverty alleviation.

The Social Capital theory emphasizes the significance of social connections and collective action in fostering the well-being of low-income individuals and strengthening local communities (Putnam, 2000). According to the theory, social capital encompasses the resources embedded within social networks, such as norms, trust, and social support. In the context of microcredit, social capital theory suggests that the presence of strong social networks and relationships can enhance the effectiveness of microcredit programs in addressing poverty and empowering individuals. When low-income individuals have access to supportive networks and social connections, they are more likely to receive valuable information, financial assistance, and mentoring, which can contribute to their entrepreneurial efforts and income generation (Amin, 2005). Moreover, microcredit programs that actively foster social capital within communities can lead to broader benefits beyond individual economic empowerment. As new entrepreneurs emerge and incomes increase, the positive effects ripple through the community, promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, and strengthening social cohesion (Woolcock, 1998).

Microcredit programs employ a cooperative model rooted in social capital theory, emphasizing social relationships and trust to facilitate economic transactions and collective action (Putnam, 1993). Cooperatives promote collaboration and mutual support among members, leading to improved access to

financial resources and economic opportunities. Through democratic governance and active member participation, cooperatives foster social cohesion, empowering low-income individuals to overcome financial obstacles and achieve economic empowerment. Additionally, thrift banks play a vital role in microcredit programs, aligning with financial intermediation theory by channeling savings to deficit units and enhancing financial inclusion (Santomero, 1991). Their localized approach mobilizes local savings and offers specialized financial products like microloans, empowering individuals with limited financial means to access affordable credit, thereby spurring economic activities and entrepreneurship within the community. Moreover, microcredit companies, guided by poverty alleviation and social entrepreneurship theory, provide financial services to the poor, leading to economic self-sufficiency and social upliftment (Yunus, 1999).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This research provides an understanding of how Microfinance institutions assist low-income families in stabilizing their revenue streams and saving for future needs helping families and help cope and rebuild in times of distress. This study also provides a clear presentation of the goals of financial institutions for higher income, assisting in channeling funds to the most successful employer and allowing them to expand quicker and provide even more desired goods to their employee. This is how financial institutions help to ensure economic resources are allocated.

The study aimed to determine the profile of respondents in terms of "Does your monthly income exceed 15,000 but less than 20,000?", and "Are you Married?". Moreover, to assess the Level of microcredit financing affecting low-income earners in terms of cooperatives, thrift banks, and microcredit companies. The study defines the significant difference between microcredit financing and low-income earners. The hypothesis of this study is that there is no significant difference in the type of Microcredit finance by income level and civil status.

The significance of this study lies in its timeliness and its potential contribution to the existing literature. Addressing the urgent challenges of poverty and financial exclusion faced by vulnerable populations, this research aims to deepen our understanding of the impact and effectiveness of microcredit programs. By examining the unique factors that influence the outcomes of these interventions, this study will offer valuable insights and generate new knowledge in the field of microfinance to borrowers and future researchers.

METHOD

Research Respondent

The respondents of our study will be given to low-income earners in Davao City. The ages of our respondents must be 21 years old or above and have a monthly income of above P10,000 but less than 20,000. According to Philippine Institution for Development studies (PIDS) that low income earners monthly income is ranges between 10,000 to 20,000, it also supported by the [imoney.ph/articles/middle class sector Philippines](http://imoney.ph/articles/middle-class-sector-Philippines). This study will be using Purposive sampling to select a sample population size of 100 respondents that would provide us with valuable feedback.

Research Instrument

This research will use adapted questionnaires. The research questionnaire consists of two parts, the Profile of the respondent for the first part. The second part included Microcredit Finance Affecting Low-income Earners in Davao City. The questionnaires will be distributed to 100 low-income earners. These respondents are requested to complete the second part of the questionnaire. The questions are measured on Likert scale.

Scale of Instrument

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.0	Strongly Agree	Strongly agree that Microcredit finance has an impact on the low income earners.
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	Agree that Microcredit finance has an impact on the low income earners.
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral	Neutral that Microcredit finance has an impact on the low income earners.
2	1.91-2.60	Disagree	Disagree that Microcredit finance has an impact on low income earners.
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree that Microcredit Finance has an impact on the low income earners.

Research Design and Procedure

This study used a quantitative research design as it involves collecting and analyzing numerical data. According to Bhandari (2021), the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data is known as quantitative research. It can be used to discover patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to larger populations. This study used a non-parametric method also known as a distribution-free test. According to CFI (2022), nonparametric tests are statistical analysis methods that do not require a distribution to meet the required assumptions to be analyzed (especially if the data is not normally distributed).

Moreover, the researchers followed these steps in gathering significant data for the study. First, the researchers prepared the questionnaire and ask permission to conduct the study. Next, Upon validation and approval, the questionnaires were explained and disseminated to the local low income-earners who have an impact on microcredit financing in Davao. Next, the researchers retrieved the questionnaire from the respondents right after they answer the survey. Next, the data gathered from the survey will be collated and tallied by the researchers and lastly The raw scores will be submitted to the statistician and were statistically analyzed and interpreted.

In interpreting the results found by this study, the collected data were analyzed using the following statistical tools: Variance is an indicator of how spread out a set of data is around its mean or average value. It is determined as the average of the squared deviations between each data point and the mean. ANOVA: Two-factor without replication Factorial analysis, also referred to as two-factor ANOVA, is a development of one-way analysis of variance. Instead of just one variable as in a single factor analysis, there are two in a two-factor analysis. It is presumption that the dependent variable is impacted by both variables or factors. Each factor has two or more classes, and each variable's degree of freedom is one lower than the total number of levels.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study addressing specific objectives are discussed in this chapter and the interpretation and analysis of the results. Tables are used to explain the outcome of the analysis.

Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Socio-demographic information.

Categories (Civil status - Income)	Frequency	Percentage
Married - Greater than PHP 15,000.00	22	0.22
Unmarried - At most PHP 15,000.00	21	0.21
Married - At most PHP 15,000.00	8	0.08
Unmarried - Greater than PHP 15,000.00	49	0.49

The table shows that most of the respondents are unmarried individuals with income greater than PHP 15,000.00, accounting for 49% of the sample. In terms of frequency, this group is then followed by married individuals with incomes of greater than PHP 15,000.00 at 22%, while 21% of the total respondents are represented by unmarried individuals with income of at most PHP 15,000.00. Widows and spinsters might own property on their own. It is not unexpected that they take up more space in the records of borrowers that are still in existence; in fact, about 90% of female borrowers seem to be unmarried. There are several ways to determine this, the most popular of which is when the occupations of borrowers are listed in various borrower lists. There are instances where being a widow or a spinster is described as an occupation, as if it were equivalent to working as a farmer or labourer (Hollis, 1999). Also, Married women have a higher probability of achieving personal empowerment than single women because they are responsible for more

responsibilities. Due to their marital status, married women also have a greater possibility of obtaining microcredit.

Married women are 0.01 times more likely than single women to experience personal empowerment, whereas married women are 0.48 times more likely to experience economic empowerment (Ali, 2020).

Table 2. Average of statistic.

Variable	Mean	Std.Dev.	Description
Cooperative	3.64	0.71	Agree
Thrift Bank	3.58	0.11	Agree
Microcredit Companies	3.83	0.18	Agree
Overall	3.68	0.12	Agree

Table 2 present the means of the respondent based on the variables identified in the study. It signifies that the overall mean (3.68) of the respondents agreed with the items or statement mention in terms of Cooperative, Thrift bank and Microcredit Companies. Microfinance organizations reduce poverty by offering small loans, savings accounts, and insurance services to underserved individuals, empowering them to start businesses, increase income, save money, and manage financial risks. They promote inclusive economic growth and alleviate poverty by addressing specific needs (Tafamel 2019).

Analysis of Variance

When utilizing an RCBD, it is paramount to correctly set the blocking of the groups of respondents involved to minimize the unaccounted variability of the error term, as much as possible. Since we have two characteristics measured during the study implementation, we can consolidate them in order to create a total of four (4) inclusive blocks. This is done by pairing each civil status with each income category, as seen in Table 1.

Performing the ANOVA two-factor test without replication, the answers to the proponent's research questions were obtained. In an ANOVA test, the results are significant if the means of different blocks under a specific treatment are statistically different from each other. There is a significant difference if the p-value associated with the blocking is lesser than the assumed alpha level. In this study, the proponents used an alpha level of 0.05. In his research of Grameen Bank participants in Bangladesh, for instance, Hossain (1988) discovered considerable effects of the influence of microcredit programs on poverty reduction. Higher levels of income, capital accumulation, and employment were evidenced among loan recipients. According to Khandker (1998), in a similar vein, that microcredit institution loans helped 5% of Bangladeshi households to transcend poverty. Both studies discovered that when microcredit programs were implemented, total employment and wage rates increased throughout the town

Table 3. Summary of the descriptive statistic.

Summary	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Married-Greater than PHP 15,000	3	10.7363	3.5787	1.0152
Unmarried-At most PHP 15,000	3	11.5523	3.8507	0.0383
Married - At most PHP 15,000	3	10.275	3.425	0.0018
Unmarried-greater than PHP 15,000	3	10.8449	3.6149	0.0102
Coop	4	14.3359	3.5839	0.0253
Thrift	4	14.1394	3.5348	0.0163
Micro	4	14.9332	3.7333	0.0665

Table 3 shows the summary of the descriptive statistics. The summary table shows the descriptive statistics of the data, including the count of observations per group, their sum, average, and variance. Looking at the means of the preference in using microcredit finance across the four (4) categories of income and civil status, the unmarried individuals with incomes of up to PHP 15,000.00 only have the highest level of preferability to microcredit finance, with a mean of roughly 3.85. Referring to the scale instrument, this value translates to agreeing that microcredit has an impact on low-income earners. This was followed by the means of the preferability in microcredit for low-income earners with incomes of greater than PHP 15,000.00; the unmarried with income of greater than PHP 15,000.00 had a mean of 3.61, while the married with the same income category had a mean of 3.57. The individuals under the married with at most PHP15,000.00 income group had the least mean level of preference for microcredit finance, with a mean of 3.42. All group means revealed that all 100 respondents agree that microcredit finance has an

impact on low-income earners. A similar finding was revealed in the case study of Bwambale et al. (2021) of the Luwero District in Uganda, where the researchers have found that microfinance do provide low-income earners with the capacity to help pay for their families' needs. In fact, in their study, an overall mean score of 3.81 was recorded, indicating that microfinance clients agree that the microfinance services allowed their families to achieve their basic needs; leading them to become more financially capable.

Table 4. ANOVA: Two-Factor Without Replication results.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Civil status - Income	0.2789	3	0.0929	12.1510	0.0058	4.7570
Type of Microcreditv	0.2789	3	0.0929	12.1510	0.0058	4.7570
Error	0.2789	3	0.0929	12.1510	0.0058	4.7570
Total	0.4103	11				

Running the ANOVA two-factor test without replication at 95% confidence level (an alpha level of 0.05) revealed that the civil status - income groups have a statistically significant effect on the preference of earners towards using microcredit finance ($F=12.15102$, $df=3$, $p\text{-value}=0.005838$). This suggests that we can reject the null hypothesis. Hence, we conclude that there is a statistically significant difference in the preference towards microcredit finance between the four civil statuses - income groups. In other words, there is a reason to believe that the preference towards availing microcredit finance is varied among different earners grouped by their civil status and income level. Advocated for the use of comparisons between "good borrowers" and failing borrowers as a key tool in managing bad debt

for institutions. Their research supported the idea that factors influencing credit behaviour include income level, prior experience in carrying out economic activities, credit terms, the number of employees at the small business, the length of time the borrower has lived in the town, their civil status, and the number of children (Bekerman and Ozomek, 2003)

There is a statistically significant difference in the preference towards microcredit finance between different types of microcredit finance products availed since the ANOVA test revealed a p-value of 0.042699 (lesser than the alpha level of 0.05). Another presumption is that a person's education level generally affects how good a borrower they are by improving their ability to manage their investments, money, and income-generating activities (Renaud and Iglesias, 2008). Regarding civil status, we stress that cohabiting debtors may receive additional or alternative income from their spouse, which could serve as a guarantee in the event of an emergency.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

According to the results of the ANOVA analysis, there is a statistically significant difference in the preference for microcredit financing among earners who are categorized according to their civil status and income level. The ANOVA test yielded a p-value of 0.042699, which is lower than the 0.05 alpha level anticipated, denoting a significant difference. This suggests that different income and social status groups have varying preferences for obtaining microcredit financing.

The cooperative variable has an average value of 3.583979, derived from a total of 4 observations. The sum of these observations is 14.33592. The relatively small variance of 0.025385 indicates that the values are clustered closely around the mean.

The theory that aligns with the cooperative variable is Social Capital Theory. This theory emphasizes the significance of social networks, relationships, and cooperation in generating economic and social benefits.

The thrift bank variable has an average value of 3.534872, based on 4 observations. The sum of these observations is 14.13949, and the variance is 0.016351. This indicates that the thrift bank variable tends to have a consistent average value with relatively low variability among the observations.

Financial Intermediation Theory is associated with the thrift bank variable. This theory focuses on the role of banks and financial institutions in mobilizing savings and directing them towards productive investments.

The microcredit companies' variable stands out with the highest mean value of 3.73331 among the variables. This average is calculated from a set of 4 observations, with a sum of 14.93324 and a variance of 0.066556. It indicates that microcredit companies tend to have the highest average value compared to the other variables. Furthermore, there is a moderate level of variability around this mean, suggesting some fluctuations in the values of the microcredit companies' variable.

The theory linked to microcredit companies is the Poverty Alleviation and Social Entrepreneurship Theory. This theory emphasizes the use of microcredit and entrepreneurial approaches to address poverty and create positive social impact.

Overall, the variable means represent the average values within their respective categories. The theories associated with each variable provide insights into the underlying concepts. The cooperative is related to social capital theory, thrift banks are associated with financial intermediation theory, and microcredit companies align with poverty alleviation and social entrepreneurship.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were drawn:

Microfinance institutions and entities must work immediately to investigate potential for deployment in new markets that have lower risk and higher return. To develop and use new and creative work processes that are suitable with the current conditions and anticipated future conditions in each government or area, the institutions must individually prepare development and adaptation plans for each institution. For the purpose of fostering innovation that can result in

unexpected solutions, these plans must be in accordance with the policies of each organization.

Borrowers, they are recommended to know what microcredit finance institution they will going to loan. They should be alert and know the rules and regulation to that institution to prevent scam and fraud.

Thrift banks, As the result shown that thrift bank has the lowest mean above all the variable with a mean of 5.534872, they are recommended to know what are their main target customer and what are their customer willingness to join. In that way they will know how much interest to a loan they will give to a borrowers.

To future researchers, they are recommended to try to study more on how to have more and reliable micro-credits finance or agency that can help even those who are not capable to have a job to be able to loan and use the money to start a new business or make them find a job to pay the interest of the loan requires.

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